

Systematisation of Experience

Internal documentation

Enabling intersectional nature recreation and biodiversity stewardship for urban resilience

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PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

List of abbreviations and acronyms

SoE Systematisation of Experience

M98 Kartlegging og verdsetting av friluftslivsområde (~ a national guidance for municipal mapping and valuation of outdoor nature recreational areas)

NINA Norwegian Institute for Nature research

OOF Oslo og Omland Friluftsråd (~ Greater Oslo Council for Outdoor Recreation)

IFZ Inter-Disciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture

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Set-up of the Systematisation

- The SoE facilitation team was composed by David N. Barton and Yennie K. Bredin from NINA.
- The workshops were held back-to-back in one morning and one afternoon. The morning session was dedicated to the pre-analyses step. The afternoon session was dedicated to analysing and reflecting on our opportunities to do transformative work for children with disabilities in the field of outdoor nature recreation (policies, planning, inclusion, etc.), as researchers and practitioners.
- The workshop(s) was held on February 14th, 2025, from 8:00-16:00 with the following representatives from OOF and NINA:
 - Reidun Bolsø, Johan Hval, Alexander Engen Aas-Hansen, David N. Barton, Vegard Gundersen, Helene Figari, Tuva Beyer Broch, and Yennie K. Bredin.

Context

Social context

Spending time in nature through outdoor recreation activities has been firmly linked to reduced stress and better physical and mental health (Wolch et al., 2014). Outdoor recreation is moreover an arena for connecting with wildlife and nature, thereby promoting awareness about its intrinsic value. Hence, from an anthropocentric as well as an ecocentric point of view, outdoor recreation has the potential of influencing societal prioritization towards the preservation and restoration of biodiversity.

In the struggle over scarce land resources, biodiversity is nevertheless systematically deprioritized against large infrastructure projects supporting for example the production of energy and goods, transportation and housing. The competition over land is particularly evident in cities. Approximately 75% of the European population now live in urban areas (United Nations, 2019) where biodiversity degradation has immediate effect people's everyday life, with, among other things, reduced opportunities for recreational activities that take place in natural areas.

Oslo Municipality's own Green Accounts estimate an average of 60m² of protected green space per resident (Oslo kommune, 2018). This varies from 18m² to 463m² by city district depending on population density and greenspace area. Urbanization is often accompanied by rising socio-economic inequality (Glaeser et al., 2009) which tends to manifest spatially by the unequal distribution of access to urban nature. In the European context, the strongest urban densification over the last three decades has taken place in the Nordic countries, and Oslo has been in front with a particularly high increase in population density (Næss, 2022). Despite its reputation as one of the greenest cities in the world (Huang et al., 2021), Oslo stands out as a city with a particularly strong and persistent pattern of geographical segregation of wealth (Haandrikman et al., 2021; Haandrikman et al., 2023; Venter et al., 2023). A recent study demonstrated that approximately 55–76 % of the Oslo population now live in areas that do not satisfy the World Health Organisation's targets for exposure to green space (Barboza et al., 2021). Access to greenspace and water is unequally distributed

across socio-economic segments of the population (seaside, lakes, rivers) (Venter et al., 2023). Considering this development, there is an urgent need for improved urban planning processes that take vulnerable groups' needs for access to natural spaces into account.

According to the United Nations, women, children, older persons and persons with disabilities that live in cities are particularly dependent on easy access to safe, inclusive and accessible green and public spaces to live healthy and good lives (Daniel, 2015). The Oslo case study is oriented towards persons at the intersection between two of these groups, namely children and people with disabilities. Child activities in Norway have become steadily more adult-organized (Skår et al., 2016; Skår & and Krogh, 2009). Less free time is spent outdoors in nature-like environments, and social differentiation in outdoor recreation is increasing, not least since the covid pandemics (Gundersen et al., 2024) Remmen & Iversen (2023) have assessed social inclusion and differentiation among children and youth in outdoor recreation activities in Oslo. One conclusion is that organized recreation activities are biased in the sense that not all age groups are equally included. Moreover, there are very few organized outdoor recreation activities for children and youth with disabilities (see also Klima- og Miljødepartementet, 2016).

In everyday life it is the residential green space that seems to have the greatest impact on children's health and well-being (Engemann et al., 2019). However, children have very little impact on the planning of outdoor recreation areas. They are usually spoken on behalf of rather than with (Vidal & Castro Seixas, 2022). Since children with disabilities seem to be the less included group in outdoor recreation, we suspect that being both children and disabled entails a double disadvantage when it comes to influencing planning and prioritization of outdoor recreation areas (Porębska et al., 2021).

The aim of the Oslo case study has been twofold:

- 1) At the level that we refer to as the "macrolevel" we have aimed to analyse strengths and blind spots in existing valuation maps of recreational areas in Oslo (called M98 maps), regarding the inclusion of vulnerable or "invisible" groups, focusing on children with disabilities.
- 2) At the level that we refer to as the "microlevel" we have aimed at getting an overview over existing actors in the field and extant activities and offers of outdoor nature recreation for children and young people with disabilities to understand what the bottle necks and opportunities are for this group to practice and participate in Norwegian outdoor nature recreation.

At the macrolevel of our case study, we evaluate municipal planning / mapping of important green spaces for recreation, used or not used in municipal planning. We try to assess how much of the mapping and evaluation was participatory and inclusive of minority groups. We have done so through a survey that was distributed to the municipalities of the greater Oslo area, i.e. OOF member municipalities in the spring of 2024. As only one third of the 18 municipalities responded, this work was later expanded to include personal interviews with the remaining municipalities in the autumn of 2024. To share results and feed into ongoing processes, NINA and OOF

held presentations at a Conference on Biodiversity and Recreation in Oslo on June 6th, 2024, and we contributed a public hearing document about potential improvements to the M98 methodology and guide in November 2024. Potentially, we may also seek leverage points for change of recreation in planning process and discuss leveraging the knowledge into other networks and work where OOF and NINA participates (e.g. consultancies on recreation mapping and valuation methods; ecosystem accounting consultancies; opportunities & actions in the Year of Recreation 2025).

At the microlevel of our case, we piggybacked on a national survey about children's outdoor recreational activities where we got to include a question about whether the children had any disability. We let ourselves inspire from Institutional ethnography (Deveau, 2008) as we recruited experts on being young, living with disabilities, practicing outdoor nature recreation, and making outdoor nature recreation accessible to children and young people with disabilities. We thus built an expert network around mentors with disabilities, recruiting parents of children with disabilities, and inviting representatives and volunteers from voluntary outdoor nature recreation organisations. In addition to the system mappings exercise that we did with the expert network we arranged focus group interviews with representatives from voluntary outdoor nature recreation organisations and we engaged in participatory observations during outdoor recreation activities and camps organized for children with disabilities.

PLANET4B project context

Because it was a requirement from the project to set up a "learning community", we established an expert network and involved them in the systems and leverage points mapping exercises. We felt that these exercises were excessively academic and that this part of the work could have been done differently by the academic partners from NINA, had this flexibility had been given to them. It did not feel right or ethical to make use of the expert network members' valuable time and knowledge in this way.

Institutional context

In Norway outdoor nature recreation is mostly unorganised or organised by voluntary organisations and groups. In the Norwegian White Paper on outdoor nature recreation (Klima- og Miljødepartementet, 2016), the Norwegian government define outdoor nature recreation as "Physical activity and spending time in nature during leisure time, with the aim of environmental change and experiencing nature". In the same White Paper, the Norwegian government postulates that outdoor nature recreation "is an important part of Norwegian national identity and cultural heritage" and "a central part of the personal identity for many people" (Klima- og Miljødepartementet, 2016). As such outdoor nature recreation in Norway may be understood as a national institution. On the relationship between outdoor nature recreation and biodiversity the White Paper says that "A rich biodiversity enriches the outdoor nature recreation experience. Therefore, preserving biodiversity is also an important contribution to facilitating outdoor nature recreation, both in terms of protecting natural areas and in terms of the nature experiences that rich biodiversity represents" (Klima- og Miljødepartementet, 2016).

Policy context

"Over 80% of Norwegian Municipalities have mapped and assessed their outdoor recreation areas using a national guidance for municipal mapping of recreation areas (Miljødirektoratet, 2014, henceforth "M98"). The M98 methodology aims to secure quality in mapping and assessment of the relative value of 11 recreation area types using local expertise. Ideally, the method should engage local residents through participation in working groups. The methodology is composed of seven main criteria (e.g., user frequency, symbolic value, and function) and six supporting criteria (e.g., accessibility, and potential use). Based on these criteria, recreational areas are valued on a scale (A-D). National government guidelines (T/2-16) recommend that municipalities avoid development of A and B value recreation areas. Each recreation area should also be described in terms of its key characteristics of importance for planning. If recreation areas are identified as important for children, this leads to requirements for an Environment Impact Assessment of any proposed development. The PLANET4B project in the Oslo area has focused on the extent to which importance for children and people with disabilities are identified in these area descriptions.

Framework for Systematisation

The Framework for the Systematisation was elaborated on by the facilitation team with help and input from Sandra Karner from the Inter-Disciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture (IFZ) and Petra Herout from Training and consultation at eye level. Because we had split our case study and worked at two different levels, at the municipal planning level (aka macrolevel) and at the individual or organisational level (aka microlevel) it was important for us to bring these two levels back together. We therefore wanted to use the SoE workshop as an opportunity to tie the different parts of our work into one big story around making nature recreation experiences accessible for children with disabilities without negatively impacting nature, and to reflect on how we, through our work, (could) contribute to a change for the better.

Objectives

The specific purpose of our workshop was to comply with the commitment of doing an SoE for PLANET4B. We used the SoE as an opportunity for us to reflect on (1) learning outcomes that have been important for OOF and NINA and that we wish to build on, (2) impacts that our work has had or may have in society, and (3) lessons that we wish to highlight and share with the rest of the PLANET4B project group.

Subject

We focused on the work and processes that we have had at the macro- and microlevels of our case study from the perspective of the case study team. We all prepared for the systematisation by reflecting on what transformative change story we might tell from the work that we had contributed to and how that story might relate to the work done by others within our team. Following up on these stories, we reflected on what a collective story from our composite case study might look like. We then reflected on what learning outcomes we might wish to build on in OOF and NINA, what impact our work has had or might have beyond the project, i.e. in society, and what lessons we might share with the PLANET4B community.

Central Aspects

Central aspects for the SoE were the different activities, discussions and undertakings that we had engaged with at the macro-, and microlevels of our case (e.g. survey of municipalities' mapping and valuation processes and use of the resulting maps, expert network meetings, interviews, participatory observations, etc.).

Central to our case study was a tension between the municipal mapping and planning level and the opportunities for engaging in outdoor nature recreation at the individual level for children and young people with disabilities. Terminology and a fear of doing something wrong has been another important element for our work at the microlevel of the case study.

Outcomes

Reconstruction of experience

All OOF and NINA case study team members came prepared with notes and reflections on what the most important or critical activities had been in shaping our work. We transferred the notes and reflections onto post-its and put the post-its on a physical timeline running from January 2023 to December 2024 on one of the meeting room walls. We then talked each other through what had happened, who had participated, why and how the activities had been important for our work. During a short break we all had the opportunity to look at the timeline, add missing and group similar or the same activities represented on multiple post-its. After the break we reviewed and agreed on the groupings and chronology of activities and proceeded to the second phase of the reconstruction process.

In the second phase of our reconstruction of experiences each workshop participant had been tasked with preparing a transformational story based on our work at the macro-, and microlevels. We had been challenged to think of how we could tie the stories told from our perspectives to the work done by other team members in the case study. The aim of the story-telling exercise was for us to reflect on how our work and research (may) contribute positively, or to a positive change, for children and young people with disabilities, biodiversity and nature. Each participant was given five minutes to tell their story. During this exercise no one was allowed to ask questions or comment on what was being told. Instead, the listeners were tasked to actively listen and take note of how the different stories tied to their own story.

Pictures from the reconstruction process and the individual change stories from the reconstruction of experiences are shared in the Appendix.

Critical analysis

After lunch we proceeded to the critical analysis of the SoE. For this step we began by revisiting the timeline and putting stickers on post-its representing critical decisions, turning points and significant elements for our work. Post-its that received two or more stickers, were identified as key turning points or significant elements by at least two case study members. Key decisions and points are briefly explained in bullet-points below.

- The case study was split into a macro- and micro level, early spring 2023 – Splitting the case into these parallel paths was important for the context or framing of our work. At the time it made sense to proceed in this way. It meant that we did not need to force things that didn't fit to come together.
- Alexander came into the project group, spring 2023 – Before Alexander entered our team there was a lack of contact between OOF and NINA. Alexander became a link and kept both sides updated. For OOF, Alexander worked practically outside with people. At the same time, he was working on an MSc, which is academic. Thus, Alexander knew both worlds and became a link in the middle. His addition to the team contributed continuity and depth to the case study with his MSc thesis and critical capacity when Johan and Reidun didn't have time.
- Contact with the Sunnaas Foundation, July 2023 – The Sunnaas Foundation was very open and accommodating, with a unique focus on use of nature in rehabilitation. Participating as observers during one of their camps was an eyeopener for us in terms of their mentor program.
- Digital meeting with the Sunnaas Foundation, September 2023 – We contacted the Sunnaas Foundation to ask if they might help us recruit some of their mentors for our learning community, which we wanted to build as a network of experts that we could learn from. The feedback that we got from the Sunnaas Foundation and their views on our ideas were critical to us feeling secure about the path that we had chosen for the microlevel of the case. The Sunnaas Foundation was enthusiastic about their mentoring scheme and peer leaders who help others. They had such a good experience with the program that they wanted to spread it further. Peer leaders are a type of resource who has been in the situation and has their own experiences, but has moved forward, mastered it. They are therefore important as role models. The Sunnaas Foundation would be happy to assist us in our work. Finally, there were some who believed in our work.
- Institutional ethnography + Expert network meeting, September-October 2023 – Building on the idea of an expert network, Helene suggested that we could lean on Institutional ethnography for our work. Letting our work be inspired by Institutional ethnography we decided that we would tackle the systems mapping challenge by mapping the institution / system from the inside out. Institutional ethnography postulates that by following the person or group that matters, you will gradually get a map of the institutions/world. We decided to build our network and map around the mentors. We had our first meeting with the mentors online on October 5th, 2023. This was followed by a digital meeting with Sunnaas Foundation on November 10th, 2023, an in-person meeting with the expert network on December 5th, 2023, a hybrid meeting with the expert network on March 3rd, 2024, and a final, in-person meeting with the expert network on June 25th, 2024. By listening to the mentors, we learned much. Their input was crucial for some of the choices that we made, for instance regarding the choice of interviewees for the focus group interviews.
- Last meeting with the mentors, June 2024 – In this meeting we shook off some of the fear of saying or doing something wrong. A lot needs to be done on many levels. By listening to the mentors, Reidun realized that there was a lot she didn't understand.

Are there systematic differences between different disabilities? Do we have what we need?

- Discover the neighbourhood, January 2024 – NINA was invited by OOF to attend a 'Discover the neighbourhood' network meeting where OOF is a member. 'Discover the neighbourhood' is a network that have come from the bottom up. It includes sports and ski associations, the Norwegian Directorate of Health, municipalities, outdoor recreation organizations, and public health contacts in municipalities. It is an arena for sharing experiences across different organisations. In this meeting, Alexander presented findings from the focus group interviews with outdoor nature recreation organisations. Suddenly, we found ourselves in a network where we could see common challenges and interests across the different organisations and sectors represented at the meeting. The sports sector also struggles financially and with promoting accessible offers – getting information out to people.
- Plan the macro case and meet with Norwegian Environment Agency, spring 2023 – We received a lot of feedback on the questionnaire about the municipalities' experience with mapping and valuing outdoor recreational spaces following the M98 instructions. The Norwegian Environment Agency had just received information that the M98 instructions would be revised, and NINA was engaged to develop some part of the methodology (Barton et al., 2025). The Oslo recreational case was thus informed that the work they were doing was useful and that there was a recipient for their outputs. The impression that the case study team had was that the methodology may be fine on paper, but that work must be done to get municipalities to use the information and keep it up to date.
- Interviews with municipalities regarding their experiences with M98, spring-autumn 2024 – The macrolevel case team learned a lot about how different the municipalities are in terms of context and the person(s) working there. For some, the mapping and valuation of outdoor nature recreation areas according to M98 was something that had been done many years ago and that was not used. Other municipalities kept the information/maps up to date. For other municipalities, no responsible person could be found.

Analysis of reasons for change

Moving on with our analysis, we began to search for connections between the macro-, and microlevels of our work. We asked ourselves what the connections were and how we could tie the different part together into one coherent story.

We found that different expertise was and had been involved in the project. The initial separation of the macro- and microlevels of our work had been a practical solution that allowed for approaching the case study theme from different but complementary angles. Now, several points for collaboration are emerging.

At the onset of the case study, we had to fit into the "straitjacket" provided by the project with a system-critical interpretation of intersectionality and focus on discrimination. We began to search for opportunities of barrier-free outdoor nature recreation with a focus on barriers and limitations. We were allowed additional questions in the national survey of parents about their children's habits and time spent on different activities and

outdoors. We found that there were differences in children's habits and activities between those with and without disabilities. Through interviews with municipalities about their experiences with the M98 method we became aware of the importance of resource persons for participation in mapping and valuing nature and outdoor environments. Through the expert network meetings and participatory observations, we became aware of the mentoring scheme, the importance of mindset and of shifting focusing from obstacles to thinking about opportunities and tools. Barriers are important in relation to physical adaptation, but at the individual level, it is important to think about opportunities. Where should we use the term barrier? It comes into the system-critical thinking. Preferably, we should work with barriers at an analytical level.

Currently OOF is considering how to include opportunities of outdoor nature recreation for people with disabilities as a concrete target group in their revised strategy. There is also a call for adaptation criteria that consider the structure/system that ensures updating and use of information in M98.

Conclusions and lessons learnt

The Most Important Learning Points with IMPACT in OOF and NINA

- When collaborating with non-researchers about research, it's important to talk early and often about how research is carried out and how large projects work. When researchers bring non-researchers into the academic world this requires good translations for all partners to be/feel equal.
- Transdisciplinary projects require time for processes to understand each other, define goals, and communicate. We have learned much about how to communicate and interact across research, interest organizations, users, target groups, and backgrounds (academic/experiences).
- Raising awareness of the use of terminology within academia versus in the "field", e.g. be able to communicate about barriers (structural) versus opportunities (personal).
- Transformative methods require time for those involved to figure out what to do after they have received the funding. In this context, the call under which PLANET4B was funded has been fantastic. It allowed us to write a project that permitted such a process. We got funding to figure out what we should do.
- We need space for processes to unfold, for including users and defining the workspace to understand concepts, shift frameworks, for methodical expansions, and learnings that broadens our horizons.
- Projects need room for changes along the way. We need space to work on the case and the concrete details and context, e.g. the complexity of outdoor recreation, nature, people, and society.
- We have learned to trust more in our own assessments, knowledge, and intuition about what is important and how things should be done in our local context. There are differences between countries and cultures. Not everything is directly transferrable or desirable.
- Through the case study, OOF has gained better knowledge in an area where they had little knowledge. Their structures have expanded. They have

contributed input on M98 and initiated a dialogue between users and organizations.

- OOF see a need to create better networks towards interest organizations and to work systematically with disabilities, internally – across members and interest organizations for broader framework conditions for outdoor recreation and disability. They have initiated knowledge sharing and experience exchange across member municipalities and member organizations.
- OOF needs a well-thought-out policy that contributes input that reduces barriers for all groups, including people with disabilities. OOF wishes to integrate people with disabilities as a target group into their strategy, concretely.
- OOF needs good training to establish offers for people with disabilities that see the individual's needs and opportunities. OOF needs internal capacity building in terms of knowledge about outdoor recreation for children and young people with disabilities (fact sheets).

The Most Important Learning Points for IMPACT in Society:

- There is a need for broader participation in planning processes, to challenge municipalities on active outdoor recreation offers and areas, and for better framework conditions for the field.
- We lack a common understanding of the challenges related to maps, participation, and engaging processes, and we need better starting points for balancing different interests and needs: nature and landscape versus interventions and development. If we can get more people into nature/outdoor recreation, will it lead to better care of nature?
- Mapping and valuation must be brought to a sufficient level that is relevant for vulnerable groups, including people with disabilities. There is a need for developing effective and realistic participation processes that ensure the inclusion of people with disabilities and data quality at a sufficient level.
- There is a need for tools that strengthen local participation and credibility in the mapping of outdoor recreation areas, for tools that make maps easy to find, and for formalized and standardized area descriptions that make the needs of (children and young people with) disabilities visible.
- Contact with nature is important for everyone. The North Star is knowing where you can go and how to get there.
- The knowledge base on outdoor recreation needs improving in planning processes. We call for a systematic overview of accessible areas and routes. Everyone must be familiar with the M98 maps so they can be used. Work for the future includes systematic updates and better routines for implementing the M98 knowledge base in planning processes.
- There is a need for spreading information (with fact sheets, petitions, etc). We need an understanding of why participation of (children and young) people with disabilities is low in outdoor nature recreation and planning processes and what is needed for this to change.

- PLANET4B, primarily through OOF, has led to greater attention to the integration of people with disabilities in outdoor recreation.
- The structures at OOF take inspiration from PLANET4B. PLANET4B has helped start a dialogue between users and researchers.
- Barriers are relevant on a structural level. It is important to see (various) limitations in context.
- Opportunities are important on an individual and social level (we must not only focus on barriers).
- We need to move from fear to generosity (openness/curiosity/allowance).
- OOF can become an important actor for increased focus and inclusion of people with disabilities. OOF can contribute to better cooperation across organizations, capacity building, and inspiration.

Learnings and Recommendations for the PLANET4B and similar projects

The following are lessons that NINA and OOF have learned through our collaboration in PLANET4B and that we wish to share with the wider project group and similar projects. In our experience, it is essential to:

- Filter information from the EU and clarify what NGOs and non-research partners really need to read and participate in.
- Help NGOs and non-research partners with reporting, understanding the EU-year, and finding/defining EU-costs including hourly rates with social costs.
- NGOs and non-research partners need “protection” from the EU project reporting processes (i.e. simplify).
- Reduce EU commission spamming!
- Connect with NGOs and non-research partners to make sure findings are understood and communicated widely.
- Reserve time for brainstorming on what needs changing and how this can be obtained through alliances.
- Start with the ‘what’, e.g. task, and then decide on the ‘how’, e.g. method best suited for the task. There needs to be context and flexibility.
- Follow closely and help NGOs and non-research partners that do not necessarily have research experience / background.

Communication of results

On May 20th we plan to invite actors from the fields of outdoor nature recreation, health, education, and the municipality sector to a workshop about making outdoor nature recreation experiences better accessible to children and young people with disabilities. We plan to briefly present observations from our case study and discuss these with the participants to challenge and consolidate our preliminary findings. After the workshop we will integrate the discussion results into our work and plan to present observations and finding from our case study in a thematic booklet. This is an accessible NINA publication format that makes information easily available to a wide range of readers. We also aim to follow-up with an online breakfast seminar in early October to present our findings to a broad range of actors within the educational-, health-, outdoor recreation-, municipal-, and political sectors.

Reflection on the 'Systematisation of Experience' method

The SoE was an opportunity for the NINA case study to really integrate lessons across the macro- and microlevels of the case study. It helped us see the advantages and disadvantages of our multi-scaled approach. We were able to work effectively at two distinct levels, while we learned that we could have sought more opportunities for knowledge integration during the process.

One of the most valuable aspects of the SoE process was the opportunity it created for honest and open dialogue across institutional and experiential boundaries. EU projects like PLANET4B are often organized around academic logics, terminologies, and deliverable structures, which can be alienating for non-academic partners. The SoE workshop gave space for experiences, doubts, and contributions from the non-academic partner, OOF, to surface more fully. Hearing how some of these experiences had not been shared earlier, partly due to discomfort with the academic framing of the project, was eye-opening. A similar structured and facilitated reflection could have helped build trust, mutual understanding, and shared ownership earlier in the project timeline too. In retrospect, such an exercise could be considered an integral part of transdisciplinary project work, not only as a concluding activity but as a way to establish more inclusive collaboration and common understanding throughout projects.

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Statement on data availability

Data used to generate this report is presented in the text above or in the appendix.

Statement on ethics

All workshop participants have agreed to the information presented in this report. We do not present or share any personal data or sensitive information in this report. All contributions from academic and non-academic participants alike are acknowledged through co-authorship of this report.